

The Effect of Pondering over Holy Quran on Science Learning Motivation of Grade Nine Students in Omani Schools

Shafiya Rashid, Shahlan Surat, Kamisah Osman

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Abstract

The Holy Quran encourages science learning and motivate humans to gain knowledge and skills "Allah will raise those who have believed among you and those who were given knowledge, by degrees. And Allah is Acquainted with what you do." (11:58). However, learning the distribution of Holy Quran verses in enhancing science learning motivation has not been investigated yet. This research investigates the effect of pondering over the Holy Quran verses in Omani schools on the students' science learning motivation. The research adopted Solomon four groups with a sample composed (94) students and applied science learning motivation scale. The result showed there are significant differences in the science learning motivation post scores between non-prettested groups fever to the experimental group. This result reveals combining between science subject and Holy Quran related science verses enhances students' science learning motivation. Thus, activating verses in science classes should be focused on in science curricula.

Introduction

The history of Oman education can be divided into three periods: the first period was before 1970, the second one between 1970, and 1997 and the third period is after 1998 until now. The education system between 1970 and 1997 was basically formed of three stages: primary education, preparatory education, and secondary education. They are respectively six years, three years, and three years. Based on the recommendation of the Oman economy conference in 1995, The Ministry of Education initiated a series of conferences and seminars with the cooperation of international organization such as UNESCO and UNSAF to develop a new education system (Al-balushi & Ambusaidi, 2015; Ambusaidi, 2016; Ambusaidi & Elzain, 2008; Council, 2017). Basic education (Education, 2001) states that " it is a unified ten years education provided by Sultanate of Oman for all children of school age." In this basic case education fulfill the primary education needs in term of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to enable them to continue their study". The curriculum was divided into three categories; first, the Islamic studies, Arabic, and social studies; the second the Science, Mathematics and Information Technology, and the third category is English Language, Environmental Life Skills, Physical Education, Art, and Music. The science curriculum in basic education differs from the old system. It is more comprehensive. It covers some components of Biology, Chemistry, Physics, and Astronomy (Al-Balushi, 2016; Ambusaidi & Elzain, 2008). Pupils are free to choose the science subjects they like and as a result, the number of students enrolled in Biology class decreases in number compared to those taking other science subjects.

Enrolment of students is a sign of interest and motivation in the learning of any subject and in this case, unfortunately, science subject especially Biology has the lowest number of students as compared to other subjects. That means Biology subject is least preferred in grade 11 and 12 and students have less motivation to study science and this could be cumulative appear from the previous class and that also affects the students' performance. For example, by tracking grade nine students' science achievement over three academic years: 2015/2016-2016/2017 and 2017/2018, more than 40% of students' grades were below average in recent years. Around 35% of students got a D in the science subject (Ministry of Education Portal 2019). When students perform poorly in Science in the local assessment it will be a predictive result for their doing in international assessment.

Student academic performance in Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and PISA (Program International Students Assessment) exams conducted by Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development was unsatisfactory for Omani stakeholders including the Ministry of Education. Both assessments focus on science and mathematics subjects besides the mother language. Omani students in students grade four and eight took exams by TIMSS and PISA. TIMSS exams evaluate students in three cognitive levels: retrieving, applying, and combining. In 2002, the Omani grade eight students in TIMSS scale was 423 points, in the following years there was a slight increase to 455 but the figure is still below the national target while

countries like Finland, Korea, Hong Kong, Japan, China and Singapore were among the top scorers in the world try to add something about the assessment of motivation (IEA, 2015; UNESCO, 2006)

Science learning motivation is a significant power that pushes students to understand the science subject and makes them active and cognitively engaged in the science lesson (Woolfolk, 2016). Therefore, enhancing students' motivation leads to improving science learning performance as a result (Giesbers, Rienties, Tempelaar, & Gijsselaers, 2013; Mohammad & Anil Job, 2012; Seli, Wammes, Risko, & Smilek, 2016). Science learning motivation can be enhanced by different ways that make learning easy and learning according to constructivism theory is made easy when the subject matter is near or within the environment of students (Omarod, 2012). Students also learn best when the content of the discussion is related to their life, this would mean teachers need to use things or culture in the society during classroom instruction. In Oman for instance, one of the books that are related to Omani students as Muslims which is in touch with their daily life is the Holy Quran. This book contains several verses that are correlated to science. Using certain or selected verses that are in accordance or similar topics with the science syllabus would be interesting as the knowledge and revelation were more than 1400 years ago while modern science merely started in the 19th century. In short, something can be done to integrate the holy Quran verses and learning science to enhance students thinking in science and increase their motivation in the subject. This can be done by developing a module based on science-related verses and test its effect on motivation among school children in Oman. Integration module between the Holy Quran and science was done in a few empirical types of research one of them was done by (Alnaka & Nedhal, 2015) that focused on the integration between the science topics and the scientific miracle verses. Their research investigated the influence of the enriching science curriculum with scientific miracle verses on developing students' scientific thinking. However, the module in current research stands on integration between the grade nine science subject and pondering over Quranic verses associated with the subject.

Literature Review

Motivation review

The term motivation briefly refers to "A driving force or forces responsible for the initiation, persistence, direction, and vigor of goal-directed behavior. It includes biological drives such as hunger, thirst, and also social forms of motivation such as the need for achievement and the need for affiliation (Colman, 2015, p. 479). While the learning motivation as defined by Tuq, Qatami, & Adas (2003) is an intrinsic or an extrinsic psychological state that forces and orients the student behavior towards goal achievement. In this research, learning motivation will be assessed by the mark the student gained on the motivation scale. Many theories were put to interpret the motivation, factors that affect it, and its effects on learning. Those theories can be divided into content motivation theories and process motivation theories. Whereas content motivation theories are interested in what is motivation and what motivates people, process motivation theories focused on how human behavior can be motivated and the relationship between the dynamic variables that make a motivation. Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Alderfer's ERG theory, McClelland-the need for achievement, affiliation and power, and Herzberg-two factor theory are examples of content motivation theories. As an instance on process motivation theories are: Skinner's reinforcement theory, Vroom's expectancy theory, Adams' equity theory, and Locke's goal-setting theory (Graham & Weiner, 1996; Venugopalan, 2007).

Based on educational psychology aims, many studies are conducted to investigate the students' motivation level and motivation theories ability to enhance motivation in educational fields and the relationship between students' motivation and students' performance. Some studies found that students with high motivation performed better compared to low motivation students and also revealed that supporting motivation can help students performing difficult exercises and maintain effort (Chowdhury & Shahabuddin, 2008; European Commission, 2013). Based on the challenges and the tracking of the Omani science education researches, there is evidence of low student motivation and academic performance. (Chowdhury & Shahabuddin, 2008) studied the relationship between students' motivation and performance and the relationship was 0.329. Al-Balushi (2016) examined the results of the motivation questionnaires given to Omani students in grades four and eight in TIMSS. The researcher found that about 66 percent of samples admitted the need to learn the science subject but only 50 percent were interested in learning science and engaged themselves during science lessons. His finding concluded that students also need some motivation and skills in learning science. In addition, some Omani studies focused on the effect of some factors and their relation with students' motivation (Al-Farsi, 2012; Al-Hadabi, 2014; Al-Ma'amari, 2008; Bait Obaid, 2014). Al-Hadabi (2014) investigated the effectiveness of a training program for science teachers based on personality type theory in developing teacher-student relationships and motivation to learn science among grades 5-12 pupils. The results illustrated that there were statistically significant differences in the teacher-student relationship as perceived by the teacher and the student, motivation to learn science for the experimental group after the experiment. However, Al-Omairi (2017) studied the relationship between emotional intelligence (EQ) skills and one of the motivation axes, curiosity among pupils in Oman school. Her study found that pupils' emotional intelligence has an impact on curiosity and students with higher EQ skills have higher curiosity levels than those with lower EQ skills. Based

on the literature review, researchers so far have yet to explore the potentials of integration of science with other non-scientific materials such as the Quranic verses on students' science learning motivation.

Pondering over the Holy Quran

Originally the Pondering over Quran Method has five steps and three levels of execution. The five steps are the introduction, reading, understanding, rehearsing, and reflection. In the introductory step, the instructor will introduce the verses and pupils will listen with an open mind. The important thing is that the pupils are to listen carefully and have the right attitude towards the selected Quranic verses. The second step is for the pupil to read the verses and the third step is to pause and understand what the ayat or verses are about. The fourth step is to repeat reading the verse to familiarize yourself with the content. The fifth step is for the pupil to reflect on the verse. Reflection involves reflection of content, the background of the verse, the context, the relation with the whole surah. Since the module is for primary school the reflection steps would be short and simple.

Science and Holy Quran

The Holy Quran was revealed to The Prophet Muhammad more than 1400 years ago for 23 years. It contains the pillars of Islam and the way of life including the shariah laws and how humans should think, believe, act and feel. Many research has shown that it is the book of miracle, explanations to phenomena (science). The Holy Quran also considers education as fundamental to men. This is explicitly understood from the first verses of the Quran, revealed to Prophet Mohammad that commanded him to seek and acquire knowledge. Allah says "Read! In the Name of your Lord, Who has created (all that exists). Has created man from a clot. Read! And your Lord is the most generous, Who has taught (the writing) by the pen, Has taught man that which he know not" (Quran, 96, 1-5) (Bucaille, 1976; Ibrahim, 2012). The Quran indeed encourages the acquisition of science and scientific knowledge and urges humans to reflect on the natural phenomena as signs of God's creation." Some scientific instruments produced in classical times in the Islamic world were inscribed with Quranic citations. Most Muslims agree that doing science is an act of religious merit, even a collective duty of the Muslim community (Bhat, 2008). Therefore, studying the effect of the Holy Quran on the learning field became a vital need.

Many types of research have been done in the area of science and the Holy Quran integration. Some of them concentrated in the experimental area (Abdulgani, 2005; Almalki, 2008; Alnaka & Nedhal, 2015; Bantain, 2011; Hamed, 2010). (Abdulgani, 2005) for example, taught the science unit of the earth and the atmosphere through the miracle in the Holy Quran. The result revealed that there are statistical differences between the control group and the experimental group in both scientific concepts understanding, and science learning attitude favor to experimental group. In the same direction, (Alnaka & Nedhal, 2015) investigated the effectiveness of enriching the content of the science curriculum with miraculous scientific contents of the Holy Quran in developing thinking skills and scientific principles for grade seven in Gaza's schools. The results proved the effectiveness of enriching the science curriculum with scientific miraculous content in the Holy Quran in developing scientific thinking skills and scientific principles where $\eta^2 = 0.84$. On other hand, some of the researchers studied some science and Holy Quran integration efforts which done in a few Islamic nations such as Malaysia, Indonesia, KSA, and Brunei Darussalam (Al-Rebiani, 2018; Latief & Rohmah, 2017; Lubis, 2015; Norazmi Anas, Engku Ahmad Alwi, Mohd Hudzari HajiRazali, Roose Nilawati Subki, & Nor Aini Abu Bakar, 2013; Salleh et al., 2011; Sunhaji, 2016; Yusoff, 2011). The rest of existed researchers tried to examine the attitudes towards the possibility of the integration between science and the Holy Quran (Al-hadabi, 2016; Hamed, 2010; Hj Othman, 2015; Mansour, 2011; Yusof & Rashid, 2015). Hamed (2010) focused on the integration between some Holy Quran verses and plant growth unit. The result showed that the integration positively affected students' scientific attitude and understanding of scientific concepts. While (Yusof & Rashid, 2015) determined students' readiness to learn science with religious sociocultural context. Their study showed a positive correlation between students' learning science attitude and religious sociocultural context (Holy Quran) $r=0.334$. In other words, it is clear that there is little or no research that investigates the impact of pondering over the Holy Quran in learning science. Therefore, this research will try to integrate related Holy Quran verses in teaching science and measure its effect among grade nine pupils in Oman.

The present study

The research aims to investigate its influence on students' science learning motivation. Therefore, the question of the research is does pondering over the Holy Quran module affects students' science learning motivation according to the groups? This research assumed there is no statistically significant difference in learning science motivation post-test mean scores between the experimental groups and the control groups.

Method

Research design

The experimental design was used to examine the influence of pondering over the Holy Quran module on students' science learning motivation. There are many experimental designs and this research used Solomon four groups design to low the influence of the pretest on research outcomes and to fulfill some of the random selection benefits. Solomon's design introduced by Solomon in 1949 and Campfle and Stanley pointed that the design is one of three one-treatment conditions experimental designs. The design has been recommended to control pretest sensitization or interaction between the pretest and the treatment. Thus the degree of both internal and external validity increases by this design (Braver & Braver, 1988). Since random selection can not be made in selecting the sample since the students distributed in a large area and the empirical works involve the selected sample be in the same class. Therefore, equivalent groups are ensuring that the distribution of the variables is equal in the groups before the treatment are given.

Sample

In the current study, the sample was a convenience sample. The selection of the sample underwent several steps: a selection of convenience governorate, a selection of convenience Wilayat, a selection of schools that consist of more than one class of ninth grade, selecting randomly experimental groups and control groups and finally selection of pre-tested groups and non- pretested groups. Based on the previous phases, the sample formed of 94 grade nine students divided into four groups as table (1) shows sample distribution.

Table 1. Distribution of the study sample

Pre-test	Experimental group	%	Control group	%
Pre-tested	26	28	21	22
Non-pre-tested	19	20	28	30

Research instruments

The learning science motivation scale is the inventory that can be used to measure the motivation level of students in learning science. In this research the researcher measured the science learning motivation by using the motivation scale published by (Glynn, Taasobshirazi, & Brickman, 2009) which has 30 items using a 5-point Likert Scale: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The scale was translated to Arabic and its content validity was determined. Its reliability was tested via 770 students by the formers, and it has high reliability. Cronbach coefficient alpha was 0.91. Besides that, reliability was retested in the Omani environment by pilot sample, the sample consisted of 28 males and 25 females. Cronbach's alpha for the pilot sample was 0.91. It consists of 30 questions and students will answer.

Developing pondering over Quran module

To developing integrated pondering over the Holy Quran module, the task, objective, target, and resources of the science curriculum in ninth grade in Sultanate of Oman were analyzed to get a rough idea of which verses are related to science curriculum content. Several verses were selected based on the literature review and researchers' experience. The list of suggested verses was judged by some experts. Then for each lesson one of the appropriate verses was selected to be used in the module designing. After that, the first draft of the module was built and evaluated by experts. As a second step, the module was modified according to experts' evaluation. The modified module was integrated with the daily plan of the grade nine science teacher.

Implementation of the module

Each of the two schools has a control group and an experimental group. For Al-Nooman bin Uday basic school for boys (5-9) students in the experimental group were pre-tested by science learning motivation scale and For

Daghmar basic school (1-10) students in the control group were pre-tested. After that, the module was implemented in science class only for experimental groups in both schools for eight weeks. After the treatment, all four groups were post-tested in motivation using the same scale.

Results and Discussion

The effect of pondering over Quran module on science learning motivation result can be determined from ANCOVA and independent test with a significance level of 5%. Before analysing the data, the normality test using one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was performed. The result of the analysis shows that the data are normally distributed ($p=.985$, $p=.971$, $p=.964$, $p=.998$) for the pre-tested experimental group (PEG), pre-tested control group (PCG), non-pre-tested experimental group (NPEG) and non-pre-tested control group (NPCG) respectively. Table (2) illustrates the result of the normality test.

PEG	N	26	
	Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	3.6427
		Std. Deviation	0.42368
	Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.09
		Positive	0.09
		Negative	-0.062
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.457
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.985
PCG	N	21	
	Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	3.9702
		Std. Deviation	0.33953
	Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.106
		Positive	0.095
		Negative	-0.106
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.488
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.971
NPEG	N	19	
	Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	4.2644
		Std. Deviation	0.21164
	Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.115
		Positive	0.109
		Negative	-0.115
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.5
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.964
NPCG	N	28	
	Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	3.8382
		Std. Deviation	0.47231
	Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.075
		Positive	0.06
		Negative	-0.075
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.396
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.998

Since the research adopts Solomon four groups design two-way ANOVA test was conducted to test the effect of the interaction between the pretest and group on the posttest scores. In other words, are there differences attributable to a particular combination of pretesting and the treatment? According to the two-way ANOVA test, the interaction between the pretest and the group on the posttest scores was significant, $F(1,90) = 21.51$, $P <$

.001. As the table (3) table of two-way ANOVA shows the main effect of the interaction between the pretest and the group yield an effect size of 0.092. Therefore, the pre-tested groups and the non-pre-tested groups data are analyzed separately.

Table 3. Two-way ANOVA

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
pretest	1.375	1	1.375	9.085	.003	.092
group	.056	1	.056	.369	.545	.004
pretest * group	3.256	1	3.256	21.513	.000	.193
Error	13.623	90	.151			
Total	1447.635	94				
Corrected Total	18.077	93				

For the pretested groups independent sample t-test was conducted to test the homogeneity of the science learning motivation pre-test according to the group. As illustrated in table 5.3, Levene's Test for Equality of Variances showed violations, $p = .160$. The result indicates that PEG ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 0.42$) has less pre-science learning motivation mean score than PCG ($M = 3.97$, $SD = 0.34$), $t(2.045) = 4.08$, $p < .001$. The finding indicates that the learning science motivation pre-test mean score is influenced by the group at the beginning of the test. Therefore ANCOVA (analysis of covariance test) is used to test the hypothesis: there is no statistically significant difference in learning science motivation post-test mean scores between experimental groups and control groups.

Table 4. Independent sample t-test

Pretested groups		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper	
science learning motivation pretest	Equal variances assumed	2.045	.160	-4.078	45	.000	-.39082	.09584	-.58385	-.19780
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.166	44.984	.000	-.39082	.09381	-.57976	-.20189

The assumptions of ANCOVA were examined. The first assumption is the normality, it was validated, refer to table (2). The second one is the outliers, they were validated by using $g = 2.2$ (Hoaglin & Iglewicz, 1987) to detect outliers outlier labeling rule. lower quartile ($Q1 = 3.29$) and the upper quartile ($Q3 = 3.94$), the upper limit = 5.37, and the lower limit = 1.86. According to table (5), there are no outliers within students' science learning motivation post-test mean scores. The third assumption is linearity, it was validated by matrix plots where the plots indicated no linearity. The Fourth, homogeneity of regression slopes which validated, $F(1,43) = .025$, $p > 0.05$. The ANCOVA test was conducted. Based on ANCOVA test, $F(1,44) = .141$, $p = .709$ higher than .05. Thus, there are no significant differences between PEG and PCG in science learning motivation post-test. Table Levene's Test of Equality and the ANCOVA test.

Table 5. Outliers' borders

	pretested group		Value
	PEG	Highest	
science learning motivation posttest			4.57
			4.40
			4.23
			4.13

					3.97
			Lowest		2.84
					3.10
					3.13
					3.20
					3.20 ^a
	PCG		Highest		4.53
					4.33
					4.33
					4.27
					4.23
			Lowest		3.13
					3.40
					3.46
					3.73
					3.78

Table 6. Test for homogeneity of regression slopes using a general linear model

pretest groups	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3.848 ^a	3	1.283	13.163	.000
Intercept	.218	1	.218	2.234	.142
treatment	.004	1	.004	.037	.849
Meanmpr	2.318	1	2.318	23.783	.000
treatment * meanmpr	.002	1	.002	.025	.874
Error	4.191	43	.097		
Total	682.798	47			

Note meanmpr: mean scores of science learning motivation pre-test

Table 7. Levene's test of equality of error variances

pretest	F	df1	df2	Sig.
yes	.280	1	45	.600

Table 8. ANCOVA

pretest	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	
yes	Corrected Model	3.846 ^a	2	1.923	20.178	.000	.478
	Intercept	.229	1	.229	2.404	.128	.052
	meanmpr	2.600	1	2.600	27.285	.000	.383
	group	.013	1	.013	.141	.709	.003
	Error	4.193	44	.095			
	Total	682.798	47				
	Corrected Total	8.039	46				

On the other side, an independent t-test was conducted to examine the science learning motivation differences between non-prettested groups. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances showed no violations, $p=.004$ result indicates that NPEG ($M=4.26$, $SD=0.21$) has more science learning motivation than NPCG ($M=3.84$, $SD=0.47$), $t(40.08)= 4.19$, $p< .001$, Cohen's $D=1.15$ which is large according to Cohen's (1988) guidelines, $r=0.50$. Table (9) indicates the independent sample t-test.

Table 9.Independent sample t-test

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
							Lower	Upper
9.194	.004	3.681	45	.001	.42617	.11579	.19296	.65939
		4.194	40.079	.000	.42617	.10161	.22083	.63152

Discussion & conclusion

The result display that the pondering over the Holy Quran module influenced the science learning motivation for non-prettested groups. This result is consistent with research done by (Yusof & Rashid, 2015) which displayed that there is a positive relationship between students' perception of science religion-interaction and student attitude towards science. It is also agreed with the study conducted by (Hamjah, Ismail, Rasit, & Rozali, 2011) that studied the method of increasing learning motivation among 291 students. They found 58.4% of respondents were motivated to learn because they recite the Holy Quran. This result also is in a line with the study of (Hamed, 2010) which found scientific attitude increased by applying scientific miracles in the Holy Quran in teaching the unit of stages of plant growth in the acquisition of scientific concepts.

The change that occurs to the non-prettested experimental group compared to the pre-tested grade could be returned to several external factors may the important one is the degree of influence that the Holy Quran left in their soul and the degree of their reaction with them. Some studied showed that females more influence by the Holy Quran verses compared to males. The second factor, the way of lesson management each experimental group is in different schools. The integration between the Holy Quran and science in the field of pondering over the Holy Quran needs more studies to investigate. In addition, including the verses in the science curriculum should not confine the verses on a cursory glance.

Theoretical implications

The findings of the study supported Gestalt theory which postulates that knowledge is a component and there is no need to be divided into parts. Therefore, the theory called to integrate the subject matter that looks similar in the purpose of facilitating the learning process and making learning meaning full. The science pondering over Holy Quran module provides a good environment for students through pondering to see noticeable integration between the Holy Quran verses and science. This integration gives students a new perception in which he feels the difference between learning science separately and learning with the Holy Quran verses. thus, it helps them to understand science and cooperate during science lessons.

Pedagogical implications

Raising learners' awareness about the importance of science subject is one of the pedagogical implications of the study. As mentioned earlier, the Holy Quran considers education as a fundamental element to men and encourages them to seek scientific knowledge and properly use them in his life. Furthermore, Holy Quran urges him to reflect on the natural phenomena as signs of God's creation. This clear view makes students reorder the position of science subject among subjects they study. The verses in the module are not just focused on worship, they order humans to discover the universe and explore human body parts and the way of function. The comments act as a motivation driver. Hence, the verses form an external motivation to learn science.

Recommendations

The current study investigated the effect of pondering over the Holy Quran module on three variables: students' motivation, students' habits of mind, and students' science performance. The future study should examine other

variables such as the morality of science, accelerated learning, and environment preservation. The study applied to grade 9 students ages between 13 and 16 years, the future study can be done on grade 11 students more matured and more aware.

Acknowledgements or Notes

Please collate acknowledgements or notes in a separate section at the end of the article before the references.

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Author Information

Shafiya AlGhammari

University Kebangsaan Malaysia
Malaysia

Shahlan Surat

University Kebangsaan Malaysia
Malaysia

Kamisah Osman

University Kebangsaan Malaysia
Malaysia
